

**O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI OLIY TA’LIM, FAN VA
INNOVATSIYALAR VAZIRLIGI**

FARG‘ONA DAVLAT UNIVERSITETI

**INGLIZ FILOLOGIYASI VA
INGLIZ TILI AMALIY KURSI KAFEDRASI**

**“Raqamli dunyoda til va shaxsiyat:
ta’limda muloqot madaniyati va
tilning o‘rni” mavzusidagi Respublika
ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya to‘plam
materiallari**

17.05.2025

STYLISTIC FEATURES OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN A SCIENTIFIC TEXT

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Abstract: The main purpose of this research is to identify the stylistic features of phraseological units in scientific texts, which will allow a deeper understanding of their role and functionality in scientific communication. The work sets the tasks of analyzing the stylistic characteristics of phraseological units, studying their functional aspects in the context of various scientific disciplines, as well as in various scientific texts. A number of scientific papers have been written on this topic. As an example, the views of various scientists on this concept are given.

Key words: phrase, phraseology, stable combinations, word combinations, phraseological units, stylistic features, scientific text, scientific discourse, scientific phraseology.

A scientific text as a special form of speech activity is a complex and multi-level phenomenon that requires from the author not only a deep understanding of the subject of the study, but also mastery of the language. In this context, phraseological units, having their own unique structure and semantic load, play an important role in the formation of the stylistics of a scientific text. Phraseology, as a field of lexicology, studies stable word combinations that not only enrich the language, but also serve as a means of expressing specific scientific concepts and ideas. Phraseological units, due to their imagery and expressiveness, are able to convey complex thoughts and concepts, which makes them indispensable in scientific communication.

Due to the fact that scientific texts contain many scientific terms, formulas and proofs, they are distinguished from other texts by their unique style, structural clarity and strict logic. Phraseological units used in such texts play a special role: they help to convey complex ideas more conveniently and effectively to the reader, but various types of phraseological units can be used differently depending on the author's purpose, the subject or specialty of the scientific text.

According to E.V. Leskova, one of the main principles of the methodological specialization of phraseological units in scientific texts is their functional load. Phraseological units can perform various tasks in the text, such as expressing a scientific concept, clarifying terminology, emphasizing the importance or relevance of the problem being studied. For example, in scientific research, the author may use the phrase “учиться на своих ошибках” to show the importance of experience and a critical approach to his analysis [5].

V.V. Vinogradov paid great attention to the stylistic specialization and coloring of phraseological units. The scientist distinguished between literary, colloquial and common phraseological units and classified their emotional coloring. By this, the linguist indicated the classification of stylistic specialization into two types: functional-stylistic and emotional-expressive [1].

Another way to convey the stylistic features of phraseological units is to use context and intonation. Emphasized intonation or a special context can convey the specific features of the meaning and style of a phraseological unit. For example, the phraseological unit “бить баклуши” can be used to convey the intonation and tone of the voice. Conveying the stylistic features of phraseological units requires a deep understanding of their meaning, structure, and context of use. The use of synonyms, context, and tone helps to convey not only the meaning, but also the stylistic coloring of phraseological units. In order to choose the most appropriate way to convey the stylistic features of

phraseological units, it is important to take into account the purpose of the speech and the reader.

Thus, proceeding from the analysis of the theoretical basis of the existing significant works devoted to the study of the methodological features of phraseological units in linguistics, it is appropriate to consider two aspects of their methodological features in the study of phraseological units. These are: functional and emotional-expressive specialization.

1) In terms of **functional-stylistic specialization**, phraseological units are divided into literary, colloquial and general-purpose types. For example, the largest methodological layer of the scientific phraseological units we are studying is colloquial units (**Russian:** бросать / бросить камешек в огород, открывать / открыть Америку, пропускать / пропустить мимо ушей, сбрасывать / сбросить со счетов; бить тревогу, злоба дня, приходить / прийти в голову, разводить / развести руками, категорическое предупреждение кому-л. о чем-л.; **English:** full steam ahead, at the double, back a winner, be (laid) или be thrown on one’s beam ends, port of call (или destination), pride of place.) that are mostly used in oral form of communication as well as in fiction.

Another methodological layer of this type is the literary units, which are used more often in written communication (**Russian:** альфа и омега, братья за перо, вводить в искушение, властитель дум, вносить свою лепту, возводить в абсолют, возводить в ранг, волею судеб, по всей вероятности, всех времен и народов, не выдерживать <никакой> критики, выйти из-под пера, выходить из-под пера, выходить на арену, вычеркивать из истории; **English:** acid test, gain ground, get into gear, get off the mark, give smb the cue, head start, heavy metal, John Doe (and Richard Roe), join (или take) issue, like one o’clock, at large, in the blink of an eye, a needle in a haystack, the tip of the iceberg, a drop in the bucket). The largest part of this layer is made up of religious phraseological units, whose etymology is traced back to religion. For

example: **Russian:** вводить в искушение, плоть от плоти и кость от кости; геркулесовы столпы, прокрустово ложе, разрубать гордиев узел [2; 3]; **English:** Adam’s ale; Society of Jesus; God’s advocate; devil’s advocate; St’Andrews cross; truce of God; Peter’s pence\penny; massacre of St. Bartholomew; Angel's trumpet tree; angels’ eyes; angel shark; death angel; destroying angel mushroom; Adam’s apple; paradise plant; sea devil [4].

2) In **emotional-expressive formation**, phraseological units are divided into types that have a bright emotional coloring, depending on the situation of speech, and those that do not express emotional-expressive coloring. For example, in scientific phraseological units specific to speech, humor, sarcasm, discontent, criticism, hatred are expressed (**Russian:** в розовом свете, витать в заоблачных высях, к красному словцу, крепкий орешек, между небом и землей, палочка-выручалочка, закрывать глаза, медвежья услуга, ни к селу, ни к городу, облечь в плоть и кровь, привешивать ярлыки, приходиться со своим аршином, размениваться на мелочи, внести свою лепту, вопрос жизни и смерти, под эгидой, поднимать на щит; **English:** cut adrift from, change of front, a, come (или draw) to a head, full steam ahead, be in free fall, at the double, acid test, cast (have или lay) an anchor to windward, cast (come to или drop) anchor, centre of gravity, close (the) ranks, comic opera, curtain drops, the.).

Thus, it is advisable to take their functional aspect, structural features, and semantic content as the basis for methodological classification of phraseological units in scientific texts. Understanding these principles allows for more effective use of phraseological units in scientific texts, and for conveying complex scientific concepts and ideas with a high degree of clarity and expressiveness.

In conclusion, phraseological units in a scientific text are an important tool that can enrich the content and form of presentation. They can give the text expressiveness, imagery and rhythm, which makes it more attractive to the

reader. However, the use of phraseological units requires care and caution so as not to violate the clarity and accuracy of the scientific presentation. It is important to find a balance between imagery and rigor, to take into account the cultural characteristics of the audience and the relevance of the expressions used. Thus, phraseological units can become not only a stylistic decoration of a scientific text, but also a tool for a deeper understanding of the phenomena under study.

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